

The Hierarchy and Distribution of Rural Service Centres In Jalgaon District (Ms)

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Abstract :

A rural service centre is a nodal place or point which provides different amenities and services to its residents as well as surrounding population. The present paper tries to find the hierarchy and distribution of rural service centres in Jalgaon district. The data used for the present work is purely secondary in nature and obtained from the district census handbook of Jalgaon district. About 18 basic services are taken into consideration while identification of a rural service centre. The function centrality index (FCI) method is used for identification of service centre. The rank orders are decided using graphical method. It is found that the number of service centres increases with increase in ranks. The existing physical factors as well as socio-cultural and economic factors, the hierarchy and distribution of rural settlements have largely influenced the spatial distribution of rural service centres.

Key Words : rural service centre, hierarchy, Jalgaon district

Introduction :

A village is an important and basic unit of planning and development. More than 65 percent population of our country resides in rural area. A service centre is a central place which provides various important facilities to its hinterland or surrounding region. A study of service centres helps to better understand the region in sharing the functions of a rural setup. It takes into account the growth poles of the region and gives a glimpse of the possible bases for expansion in the future. Planners while considering the extension of services in rural areas, know only vaguely the distribution patterns of facilities, the extent of the area, and population which are covered and which needs to be served. (Jaymala, D 1978) Rural Service centres are the growth points or settlements with relatively high intensity of functional magnitude and distinctiveness. The fundamental trait of these centres is to serve their surrounding territory in terms of cultural, commercial, administrative and other requirements (Khan, 1995). In regional space, growth does not occur everywhere and all alone, it appears in points or development poles, with variable intensities. It spreads along diverse channels with varying terminal effects to the whole of economy (Perroux, 1955). A rural service centre plays a very important role in the life of the villagers because it provides various important facilities such as medical, educational, market centres, transportation, water supply, Post and Telegraph, banking and shopping facilities to its inhabitants. Perhaps a village may better serve as a market-centre or an important location for a dispensary, or perhaps have educational facility. Village is the basic unit of settlement development. (Jaymala, D 1978) Therefore, in present study emphasis is given to understand the network of service centres with their functional hierarchy, extent of zone of influence and functional gaps in rural context.

Jalgaon district is selected for the present study because of its rural nature. The northern part of the district is occupied by the Satpura mountain ranges and is deprived of basic amenities. The study will investigate the imbalance of distribution of rural service centres in the district due to its varied geographical conditions. As the study is devoted to only rural service centres, urban area and towns are omitted from the study.

Objectives :

The presents study has framed the following objectives and an endeavor is made to attain the same.

1. To identify the rural service centres in Jalgaon district with the help of various facilities they provide.
2. To understand the distribution of rural service centres according to their hierarchical orders in Jalgaon district.

Methodology :

The Study Region :

The district under study is flanked by the Satpura ranges to the north and Ajanta hills to the south and the central part of the district is covered by well known Tapi river basin which flows towards the west. The region experiences slightly different climate than by rest of the state of Maharashtra, since it is located away from the coast but at much lower altitude that the rest of the plateau of Maharashtra. The location away from the coast has resulted in high range of mean daily temperature which is slightly than 15⁰C. Low altitude has resulted in abnormally high maximum summer temperature which is normally above 40⁰ C The district is bounded by the state of Madhya Pradesh to the north. The rivers Anner and Panjhara form a boundary in the west between the region and the Dhule district. In the east, the district under study is bordered by Buldhana district. To the south, Satmala, Ajantha and Chandor hills form a natural

boundary between the study region and the districts of Nasik and Aurangabad. The Jalgaon district which is one of the 34 districts of Maharashtra lies between 20° N and 21° N latitudes and 74° 55' E and

76° 28' E longitudes. The total area of the district is 11765.0 sq. Km. According to 2011 Census, the total population of the region was 42, 29, 917.

Map No.1

Data : The present study is mainly based on secondary data which are obtained from the District Census Handbook of Jalgaon district for the year 2011. The services available at the villages in the districts are obtained from the Village Directory section the Census Report, 2011. SoI toposheets are used to show the location map and base map of the study region.

Identification of Rural Service Centres :

Centrality of a particular centre is measured in terms of its importance regarding functional capacity to serve the needs of the people in the surrounding area (Hangaragi, 2005). It may be expressed by both either qualitatively e.g. high and low centrality or quantitatively in terms of centrality scores obtained by converting the functional base of concerned centres. Many geographers attempted to establish a precise relationship between the size of settlement in terms of population and the range of functions which it offers (Jonson, 1967). Centrality, however, depends upon the intensity of the central functions. Bhatt (1976) had used a weighting technique to compute the centrality of service centres. Some scholars have measured the functional

hierarchy of settlements on the basis of people's choice of centres to fulfil their needs (Sen *et al.*, 1971; Kayastha and Mishra, 1981; Mishra, 1985). Weighted indexing method (Sinha & Singh, 1995) was generally used to derive composite index value of a settlement based on its functional presence in context to the total functions found in the region. Since, all the functions cannot be treated equally, so weighting technique is used for computing the centrality under which functions are assigned numerical values on the basis of their relative regional importance. The weightage of functions in present study have been computed by adopting following formula (Bhat, 1976 and Mishra, 1985):

$$W_i = \frac{N}{F_i}$$

Where, W_i =Weightage of ith function

N =Total number of settlements

F_i =No. of settlements having that function

In present study, the hierarchy of service centres have been derived by using Functional Centrality Score based of Weightage method.

Functional Centrality Index value (FCI) of a particular centre has been computed by summing the weightage of all available functions of a centre and then it is divided by the total weightage of all selected centres. This may be expressed as:

$$FCI = \sum_i^n \frac{W_{ij}}{W} \times 100$$

Where, CI = Functional centrality index

W_{ij} =Weightage for jth centre

W=Total

Weightage of all the centres.

The method of identification of rural service centres is performed on all the rural settlements of the district. The weightages method is used for this purpose. The process of identification of rural service centre is based on Median Population Threshold (MPT) calculated by Reed

Muench Method (Haggett and Gunwardena, 1965). On the basis of Reed Muench method, MPT of 18 important facilities have been computed. The weightage value has been determined by first assigning an arbitrary value of 1 to the facility having lowest threshold, while the weightage value of other functions has been obtained by dividing its threshold population by the lowest threshold population in the distribution. The centrality score or functional potential of central places is the representation of total weightage value of facilities provided by the rural service centre. In Jalgaon district, there are 1487 inhabited rural settlements and all are not considered as the service centre or central place. Only the rural settlements having centrality score more than the regional average are considered as rural service centres for the present study. The following services or functions are taken into consideration for determining the centrality of a rural service centre.

Table 1: Threshold Population and Weighted Score for the Selected Functions in Jalgaon District (2011)

Sr. No.	Selected Services	Threshold Population	Weighted Scores
1	Public Bus Service	1322	1
2	Govt. Primary School	1595	1
3	Self - Help Group (SHG)	1619	1
4	Agricultural Credit Societies	1968	1
5	Govt. Middle School	2147	2
6	Sub Post Office	2242	2
7	Post Office	2408	2
8	Primary Health Sub Centre	2581	2
9	Govt. Secondary School	2816	2
10	Cooperative Bank	2980	2
11	Dispensary	3676	3
12	Commercial Bank	4136	3
13	Non Government Medical facilities Medical Practitioner	4642	4
14	Hospital Allopathic	4781	4
15	Primary Health Centre	4786	4
16	Govt. Senior Secondary School	4805	4
17	Internet Cafes / Common Service Centre (CSC)	6047	5
18	Govt. Arts and Science Degree College	10194	8

Source: Personal computation based on District Census Handbook of Jalgaon District, 2011

Results And Discussion :

Hierarchy of Rural Service Centres : The hierarchy of rural service centres refers to the arrangement of service centres according to their tier or order. Hierarchy of service centres depicts the

stratification of centres into different tier or orders. The higher order centre provide the superior level of functions both in quantitative and qualitative way and have a vast hinterland or serving zone while

lower orders provide low level of functions within a short distance. (Sarkar, 2018) A simple graphical method is used for identifying the hierarchy of rural service centres in Jalgaon district. The centrality scores of rural service centres are arranged in

descending order and are plotted in a graph. The breaks in the continuity of graph are considered as breaks in the orders. The group between two breaks is considered one order of rural service centres. These are ordered from first to fifth order.

Fig. No. 02

(i) First order service centres : Under the category of first order, there is only one service centre namely Muktainagar with centrality score about 92. Though it does not enjoy the status of Tehsil headquarters, but it is only big town in Muktainagar tehsil. Due to administrative norms, Muktainagar is a Nagar Panchayat. It is well connect with the surrounding villages with road network.

(ii) Second order service centres : There were total four second order rural service centres in Jalgaon district in 2011. These were Nashirabad (Jalgaon), Bodvad (Bodvad), Kasoda (Erاندول) and Shendurni (Jamner). All these second order service centres are large sized settlement and are as equal to small towns. The size of population of these villages is

larger, and therefore, many services are made available for the residents as well as nearby small villages.

(iii) Third order service centres : There were four villages enjoying the status of third order rural service centres in Jalgaon district. These service centres were Adawad (Chopda), Raver rural (Raver), Chinaval (Raver) and Pahur (Jamner). These are also big rural settlements and well connected with road ways with the surrounding hinterland. Therefore, enjoy the status of a rural service centre.

Table No. 02 : Hierarchical distribution of rural service centres in Jalgaon district (2011)

Sr. No.	Tehsil	I	II	III	IV	V	Total
1	Chopda	0	0	1	1	34	36
2	Yawal	0	0	0	2	36	38
3	Raver	0	0	2	1	35	38
4	Muktainagar	1	0	0	1	18	20
5	Bodvad	0	1	0	0	8	9
6	Bhusawal	0	0	0	0	27	27
7	Jalgaon	0	1	0	0	28	29
8	Erاندول	0	1	0	0	16	17
9	Dharangaon	0	0	0	0	20	20
10	Amalner	0	0	0	0	38	38

11	Parola	0	0	0	0	29	29
12	Bhadgaon	0	0	0	0	24	24
13	Chalisgaon	0	0	0	0	56	56
14	Pachora	0	0	0	1	33	34
15	Jamner	0	1	1	2	37	41
	Total	1	4	4	8	439	456

Source : District Census Handbook of Jalgaon district (2011)

(iv) Fourth order service centres : There were total eight fourth order service centres in Jalgaon district in 2011. These service centres were Dhanore (Chopda), Sakali (Yawal), Nhavi (Yawal), Nimbhore (Raver), Kurhe (Muktainagar), Nagardeola (Pachora), Pahur Kasba (Jamner) and Phattepur (Jamner). These are relatively larger sized villages having limited number of services which are provided to the inhabitants and surrounding population.

(v) Fifth order service centres : There were 439 villages identified as rural service centres at lower order i.e. fifth order. These service centres cater the need of local people with limited choices and relatively lower order of functions. Most of the service centres are equipped with basic level of services like primary school, fair price shop, post office, PCOs and family planning centres and sub-centres, primary cooperative societies, seed and fertilizer depot etc. Though these rural service centres are distributed throughout the district but the maximum concentration of these centres is found in the western and southwestern while the northern part is deprived of such centres due to physiographic inaccessibility.

Conclusion :

From the above results and discussion, it can be drawn that existing physical factors as well as socio-cultural and economic factors, the hierarchy and distribution of rural settlements have largely

influenced the spatial distribution of rural service centres. The higher order of service centres constitute comparatively larger population base which induced better demands for functions and services. The villages having large population and better connectivity with the hinterland enjoyed the status of rural service centres in Jalgaon district. These are nodal centres providing various amenities and services to the residents and surrounding population. The lower order service centres at fifth ranks are large in number due to availability of few services. But these villages are also depend on nearby bigger service centres for many services and amenities.

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